

D3.4. Ultrasound Transducer Control and Image Formation

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About ThrombUS+

Deep vein thrombosis (DVT) is the formation of a blood clot within the deep veins, most commonly those of the lower limbs, causing obstruction of blood flow. In 50% of people with DVT, the clot eventually breaks off and travels to the lung to cause pulmonary embolism. Clinical assessment of DVT is notoriously unreliable because up to 2/3 of DVT episodes are clinically silent and patients are symptom free even when pulmonary embolism has developed. Early diagnosis of DVT is crucial and despite the progress made in ultrasound imaging and plethysmography techniques, there is a need for new methods to enable continuous monitoring DVT diagnosis at the point of care.

ThrombUS+ brings together an interdisciplinary team of industrial, technology, regulatory, social science and clinical trial experts to develop a novel wearable diagnostic device for point-of-care, operator free, continuous monitoring in patients with high DVT risk. The device will combine autonomous, AI driven DVT detection based on a novel wearable ultrasound hardware, impedance plethysmography and light reflection rheography for immediate detection of blood clot formation in the lower limb. Activity and other physiological measurements will be used to provide a continuous assessment of DVT risk and support DVT prevention via serious gaming. The aggregated data will drive an intelligence decision support unit that will provide accurate monitoring and alerts. Extended reality will be used to guide experts to design exercises and patients to use the device optimally.

ThrombUS+ is intended for use by postoperative patients in the ward, during long surgical operations, cancer patients or otherwise bedridden patients at home or in care units, and women during pregnancy and postpartum. ThrombUS+ will use big data sets for AI training collected in the project via 3 large scale clinical studies and will validate the outcome in the clinical setting via 1 early feasibility study and 1 multi-center clinical trial.

Deliverable D3.4 Description

The Beamformer is a critical component of the project. It is a part of the Ultrasound Scanning Module (USM). It receives control commands and data from USM Software and manages the spatial formation, steering, and focusing of ultrasonic beams during both the transmission and reception phases. It adjusts the timing (delays) of signals across transducer array elements, transmits ultrasound pulses into the body, receives ultrasound echoes, dynamically adjusts the delays and amplitude (apodiation) during the reception phase, processes the beamformed signals, and transfers the processed data to a Central Hub Intelligence (CHI). TELEMED will also provide the device driver package (TDP) and SDK library (USGFVII) that simplify the development of CHI control software by Athena. The beamformer will also provide a physical interface to control the Wearable Actuator Module (WAM).

Task T3.4 aim is to develop a beamformer that will control transducer arrays provided by Fraunhofer and Vermon and according to general specifications defined in Product Design Specifications 3.2.1 Hardware, Table 8.

The output of Task T3.4 (i.e. Deliverable D3.4) is design files for the beamformer PCB, embedded software, driver and SDK kit, technical drawings of the housing and specifications of connectors located on the beamformer PCB.

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Terms and Definitions

Term	Definition
ADC	Analog-to-Digital Converter
AFE	Analog Front End. It is integrated circuit(s) that perform certain function specific to ultrasound imaging. The TX AFE is responsible for generating and shaping the electrical signals that drive the ultrasound transducer elements to produce acoustic waves. The RX AFE processes the weak echoes received by the transducer, converting them into signals suitable for digital processing
BF	Beamformer
CHI	ThrombUS+ Central Hub & Intelligence module
DVT	Deep Vein Thrombosis
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FPGA	Field-Programmable Gate Array. It is a type of integrated circuit that can be programmed and reprogrammed after manufacturing to perform specific tasks.
GPIO	General Purpose Input/Output
HADEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
HV MUX	High-Voltage Multiplexor Unit
I/O	Input/Output
I2C	Inter-Integrated circuit
IC	Integrated circuit
LA	Linear Array
LNA	Low Noise Amplifier
LPF	Low Pass Filter
LQFP	Low-profile Quad Flat Package
LVDS	Low-voltage differential signalling
MCU	Microcontroller Unit
MSPS	Mega Samples Per Second
RX	Receive
RX AFE	Receive Analog Front End
SDK	Software Development Kit
SPST	Single-pole, single-throw
T/R	Transmit/receive
TBD	To be done
TL	Task Leader
TX	Transmit

TX AFE	Transmit Analog Front End
USB	Universal Serial Bus
USM	ThrombUS+ Ultrasound Monitoring Module
UST	Ultrasound Transducer
WAM	ThrombUS+ Wearable Actuator Module

Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the activities and outputs related to Thrombus+ Task 3.4 “Ultrasound transducer control and image formation”. These mainly include the following: beamformer board design, beamformer housing (case), connectors, including pin map and specifications, firmware and software, and ultrasound beamforming signal processing functions. The beamformer (BF) is an essential part of the Ultrasound Module (USM), and its specifications are derived from document D6.1 “Product Design Specifications” and discussions with the project partners. The deliverable document describes the beamformer block diagram, its communications with other hardware and software components, the structure of the software modules used to control it, and drawings of the proposed beamformer housing (case).

1. Specifications of the beamformer

1.1. User requirements

The performance indicators to be considered are:

1. Image quality, in general defined by the number of channels in the beamformer and the number of crystals (elements) in the transducer.
2. Size (form-factor) – that should be as small as possible, and, ideally, wearable.
3. Components cost (price) – should be adequate to the intended use.

1.2. Proposals for preliminary designs

During initial discussions, two beamformer options were proposed by TELEMED and one option was proposed by Vermon (Figure 1):

1. 64-channel beamformer capable of controlling up to 192 transducer elements having three or more transducer connectors.
2. 32-channel beamformer capable of controlling up to 128 transducer elements with a single transducer connector having a smaller footprint.
3. Beamformer integrated with an ultrasound transducer can transfer ultrasound data wirelessly or via cable to a Central Hub Interface (CHI).

After online discussions, option 2 was selected as the one offering the best performance-to-cost ratio. Although option 3 appeared attractive, it was deemed challenging to implement within the project's framework, primarily due to its power consumption, which was estimated to be at least 5W in B mode during the scanning process. This would result in a significant amount of heat generation, making it unsuitable for a wearable device.

Figure 1. Initially proposed beamformer form-factors.

2. Beamformer purpose, technical requirements and relation with other modules

2.1. Beamformer in the ThrombUS+ system

The beamformer is a part of the Ultrasound Monitoring Module (USM)¹. The Ultrasound Monitoring Module will perform intermittent measurements for operator-independent DVT monitoring, including: a) ultrasound imaging and online segmentation of deep veins primarily in the thigh using the compression ultrasound method; b) detection of thrombosis by tracking vein localization and dimensions during pressure application with the use of the Wearable Actuator Module (WAM); c) estimation of vein blood flow perturbations caused by distal DVT using colour, power, and pulse wave Doppler imaging; and d) a continuous data stream for decision support on DVT risk, thrombosis detection, and characterization². The beamformer's task is to drive the probes developed by Vermon and FRAUNHOFER to ensure real-time ultrasound image data (including B mode, colour flow and pulse wave Doppler mode) stream and provide the synchronization outputs for the Wearable Actuator Module (WAM) to start/stop the compression cycle in correlation with the state of ultrasound imaging session.

2.2. Technical requirements

The technical requirements (Table 1) were established for the beamformer in the project planning stage #2. The last column of (Table 1) specifies the parameters of the designed beamformer with respect to the requirements.

Table 1. Implementation of beamformer's technical requirements.

ID	Description	Request (R) Wish (W)	Designed beamformer parameters
TR_USM_05	Beamformer: The beamformer must ensure B-steer scanning with linear transducer having up to 128 elements.	R	≤ 128
TR_USM_06	The beamformer must support linear scanning with RC transducer having 96 elements and phased/sectorial scanning with 32 elements	R	Supported
TR_USM_07	The beamformer must provide adjustable focusing during transmission in 8 zones and dynamic focusing during reception.	R	Supported
TR_USM_08	The beamformer must support imaging modes including B-steer for linear probes, Color Doppler, Power Doppler, Pulse Wave Doppler, and duplex in two perpendicular scanning planes (with respect of the vein direction)	R	Beamformer supports: B (steer, compound), Color, Power Doppler, Pulse Wave Doppler modes, Elastography and raw RF data modules are optional as well.

¹ Cesana J, Annunziata S, Moltani LA, Didaskalou S, Jurkonis R, Marozas V, Lukoševičius A, Schubert F, Balling S, Architectural design of the strap and sock wearable, Deliverable 2.4, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 31 December 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14352778>

² Marozas V, Kaldoudi E, Prinz T, Lukoševičius A, Jurkonis R, Eitminavičius R, Didaskalou S, Vehkaoja A, Ahola R, Slabov A, Jegelevičius D, Balling S, Moutafidou A, Daukantas S, Rapalis A. Technical and functional requirements, Deliverable 2.3, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 31 October 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13897671>

TR_USM_09	The beamformer must be connected to the Central Intelligence Hub via a USB-A or USB-C connector for both power supply and data transmission.	R	Beamformer connection USB-C
TR_USM_10	Data formats: The data format at the output of the beamformer for B-scan, Colour Doppler, and Pulse Wave Doppler modes must be an 8-bit image.	R	8-bit images ensured by TELEMED SDK.
TR_USM_11	Beamformed RF data access through an SDK library must be ensured for parametrization of ultrasound signals.	W	RF data module optionally available
TR_USM_12	The data format at the output of the beamformer for RF data must be 16 bits sampled at a rate of no less than 40 MHz.	W	Output data is 16 bits and sampled at 40 MHz.

2.3. Relationship with other modules in the ThrombUS+ system

The subsection explains how the beamformer relates to other project modules (both physical and logical relations) (Figure 1). The beamformer includes two software units (device driver and SDK library). Control of the beamformer will be managed from the Central Hub & Intelligence module (CHI). CHI will select the desired scanning mode and associated parameters from the available list via the SDK and device driver and will receive a stream of ultrasound image data (optionally raw RF data), which will be sent to the AI module for vessel detection, tracking, and vein compressibility assessment. Additionally, the synchronisation outputs of the beamformer (SCAN START/FRAME OUT) may be connected to the Wearable Actuator module (WAM) to pause or initiate the compression during the imaging (assessment) session.

Figure 2. The interaction of the beamformer with other modules.

3. Beamformer Design

3.1. Beamformer architecture

The overall beamformer architecture is presented in Figure 3 and its basic components are explained in the sections below.

Figure 3. The Block diagram of the beamformer.

3.1.1. FPGA

FPGA is main digital processing module in the beamformer (Figure 4). It is designed around Altera Cyclone V IC. Its key functions are as follow:

- Receives and stores scanning control parameters and coefficient arrays for digital signal processing from the USB controller.
- Receives data from the RX AFE, reserialises them, and performs delay-sum beamforming with per-channel apodisation and calculations to enhance image contrast.
- Buffers and sums incoming data streams to extract the inverse harmonic signal.
- Performs depth-dependent frequency filtering to optimize spatial resolution and sensitivity of the receiving chain.

- Performs a Hilbert transform to extract quadrature components (I and Q) and obtain the low-frequency envelope of the reflected signal.
- Performs logarithmic signal conversion, followed by compensation to reduce noise and low-level artefacts.
- Adjusts the dynamic range of displayed signals by modifying the transformation curve slope and signal level shift while controlling the low-signals level.
- Decimates and buffers data for transmission to the USB controller in the specified quantity and bit depth, attaching a header with scanning mode indicators and additional information about the transmitted beam.
- Uses I and Q quadrature signal components for Doppler signal detection, filtering, and processing.
- Buffers and transmits RF data to the USB controller.
- Forms data packets for transmitting colour and spectral information to the USB controller.
- Sends control signals and data arrays to the HV MUX, TX AFE, and RX AFE chips (including the AGC digital gain control curve) and programs the high-voltage value in the DAC.

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Figure 4. The functional diagram of the FPGA.

3.1.2. TX AFE

The Transmit Analog Front End (TX AFE) is designed using a highly integrated, high-performance 32-channel transmitter IC designed for ultrasound imaging systems.

Key features include:

- On-chip beamforming
- Integrated floating power supplies
- Maximum output current: 0.3A to 1.2A (configurable)
- T/R switch with 24Ω ON resistance
- Low power consumption in various modes (0.45 mW/ch in receive mode)
- Main functions of TX AFE unit are:
 - Generates high-voltage excitation pulses with specified timing parameters (pulse duration and period).
 - Provides the required number of excitation pulses for each scanning mode.
 - Ensures the necessary delay of excitation pulses for 32 independent channels (TX beamforming).
 - Sets the current of the pulsers independently for each scanning mode.
 - Connects the echo signal lines to the input circuits of the RX AFE chip using a TR switch.

3.1.3. RX AFE

The Receive Analog Front End (RX AFE) is designed around highly integrated 32-ch solution optimised for medical ultrasound applications.

Key features include:

- Configured for ADC resolution of 12 bits
- The programmed sampling rate of 40 MSPS
- Low-voltage differential signalling (LVDS) output interface
- Power consumption of approximately 38 mW per channel

Main functions of the RX AFE:

- Amplifies received echo signals in 32 channels using an LNA with programmable gain and a controlled attenuator to compensate for depth attenuation.
- Performs preliminary filtering of received signals using an LPF.
- Converts echo signals from analogue to digital format.
- Transmits digitized signals to the FPGA after converting them into a serial code (serialization).

3.1.4. HV MUX

The High-Voltage Multiplexor unit (HV MUX) ensures the switching of the sensor's high-voltage excitation pulses and reflected echo signals between 128 (maximum) elements of the piezoelectric transducer and 32 output lines of the TX AFE chip according to the scanning algorithm (moving aperture along transducers elements) for transducers. It is designed using eight 16-channel linear high-voltage analogue integrated switches.

Key features of the HV MUX chip:

- single-throw (SPST) switches
- Low on-resistance
- Integrated bleed resistors for discharging capacitive loads
- Low power dissipation and charge injection
- Packaged in a 48-pin LQFP (7mm x 7mm)

The particular IC was chosen because it does not require a dedicated high-voltage supply, simplifying system requirements. It offers excellent performance characteristics, including low off-isolation, high linearity, and fast switching times (5 μ s max turn-on time, 3.5 μ s max turn-off time)

The device utilizes a serial interface with a 16-bit shift register and transparent latch for control, allowing for efficient management of the 16 analogue switches. Each data bit in the shift register corresponds to a single analogue switch.

3.1.5. USB MCU Controller

The USB MCU Controller Module is built around the SuperSpeed USB Controller. Its purpose is to facilitate high-speed communication between the beamformer and the computer, ensuring that both envelope data and RF beamformer data are transferred to a computer, while also receiving commands from it.

Main functions of the USB MCU Controller:

- Ensures device detection and identification by the computer.
- Loads the FPGA configuration file.

- The device status is queried via the I2C bus, including the presence and type of the connected transducer, internal power supply status, temperature sensor readings, and overheat signal sources.
- Allows modification of information about the connected transducer and the firmware of the USB controller itself.
- Uses GPIO ports to enable and disable the device's internal power sources.

3.1.6. Power Converter and Power Monitor

The Power Converter and Power Monitor module are designed to supply stabilised secondary voltages and adjustable high-voltage outputs. It also features indicators for voltage levels within specified limits to ensure effective voltage monitoring.

3.1.7. I/O Module

The Inputs-Outputs Module (I/O Module) is an auxiliary board created to enhance beamformer connectivity, facilitating external control and synchronisation of signal sources, with three inputs and three outputs (Figure 5).

Main features include:

- Protects Beamformer Input and Output lines from external voltage.
- Enables the system to identify the installed I/O module.

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Figure 5. Photo of the beamformer board assembled with the installed I/O Module.

3.2. Beamformer Mechanical Design

The beamformer is designed to be inserted into an enclosure similar to a previous range of TELEMED ultrasound scanners — a square aluminium machined enclosure box that also functions as a heatsink.

Figure 6. Technical drawing showing the beamformer's mechanical components and assembly stages.

Figure 8. Labelling of the rear panel and I/O connectors.

3.4. Beamformer Insulation Diagram

AREA	INSULATION TYPE	MAX. VOLTAGE	MOOP	MOPP
A	RI	240 VAC	••	
B	RI	240 VAC	••	••
C	RI	240 VAC	••	••
D	RI	5 VDC	••	••

Figure 9. Beamformer insulation diagram

4. Software components provided with the Beamformer

The Beamformer unit is provided with essential software components, including a device driver and a Software Development Kit (Usgfw2 SDK). The device driver is specifically designed for TELEMED's beamformer, while the SDK is compatible with all devices produced by TELEMED. The device driver has been included in the TELEMED Drivers Package, and necessary functions for the beamformer project have been integrated into the SDK.

A general overview of TELEMED's software architecture, which incorporates the beamformer hardware component marked as an "Ultrasound Scanner", is illustrated in the figure below (Figure 10). Note that the components coloured in grey were developed by TELEMED, while the other components are based on Windows OS using Microsoft DirectShow technology.

To utilise the beamformer and related software, users must have a Microsoft Windows operating system (versions 8, 10, or 11) and a USB-C connection between the computer and the beamformer.

Figure 10. General TELEMED software architecture.

5. Summary and conclusions

According to the general technical requirements of the Thrombus+ project, the low-power, compact beamformer with 32 transmit/receive channels connectable to transducers with up to 128 elements was designed. The beamformer can be powered via USB-C and an external power supply. Mandatory software modules were developed for integrating the device into the project's overall workflow.

Annex 1: Beamformer Specifications

BEAMFORMER TYPE	
Delay and sum	
32 T/R channels multiplexed to maximum transducer 128 lines	
IMAGING MODES	
B	
B+B	
4B	
B+M	
M	
B-steer for linear transducers	
Compound for linear and convex transducers	
Virtual convex for linear transducers	
Colour Doppler (CFM)	
Power Doppler (PDI)	
Directional Power Doppler (DPDI)	
Pulsed Wave Doppler (PWD)	
B+PWD (Duplex)	
B+CFM+PWD (Triplex)	
Tissue Harmonic Imaging (THI, ITHI)	
RF data access using SDK library	
SCANNING METHOD	
Electronic linear	
Electronic convex	
Electronic sector (Phased Array)	
TRANSMIT	
Voltage B/M	Min $\pm 5.0 \pm 0.5V$; Max $\pm 80 \pm 2.0V$
Voltage CFM/PW	Min $\pm 5.0 \pm 0.5V$; Max $\pm 80 \pm 2.0V$
Pulse shape	Bipolar, periods number and width variable
Pulse rise/fall time	14ns from 0V to max positive amplitude/ from 0V to max negative amplitude, with load $R_L=2k\Omega$, $C_L=120pF$ 50 μs
Max delay transmit mode	Min $\pm 5.0 \pm 0.5V$; Max $\pm 80 \pm 2.0V$
Delay precision, Transmit	6.25ns
RECEIVE	
Max delay receive mode	12.5 μs

Receive channel bandwidth	20MHz
Dynamic range	102dB
COLOR DOPPLER (CFM)	
PRF variable:	0.3-10 kHz
Wall filter settings:	3 steps (5%, %10%, 15% PRF)
Gain control:	40 dB
Angle steering for linear transducers:	$\pm 25^\circ$
Real-time spatial filter:	4 values
CFM palette:	10 maps
B/Color priority control	
Color threshold control	
CFM baseline control	
Max PRF:	10kHz
Max number of cycles:	8
Flow sensitivity:	TBD
PULSE WAVE DOPPLER (PWD)	
Sample volume:	1 to 5 mm
Max PRF:	15kHz
Flow sensitivity:	TBD
DEPTH SELECTION	
2 – 31 cm (depth range depends on transducer type)	
TRANSDUCERS	
Ranging from 1.5 MHz to 18 MHz	
Multi-frequency	
Automatic transducer recognition	
FOCUSING	
Transmit:	variable, up to 16 zones
Receive:	point-to-point, dynamic
SIGNAL PROCESSING	
Lines density control for better resolution	
TGC control	
Dynamic range	
Overall gain control	
M-mode sweep speed control	
Acoustic power control	
Variable frame averaging	
Brightness, contrast	

Advanced gamma control: 8 fixed curves, 8 user-defined (custom)	
Scan direction, rotation, and up-down controls	
Negative/positive control	
Bi-linear interpolation	
Echo enhancement control	
Noise rejection function	
Speckle reduction function	
FUNCTIONS	
Cine	Recording up to 2048 frames to memory
	Play / Pause / Stop / Frame selection
	Saving ultrasound video file to disk
	Loading ultrasound video file from disk
ULTRASOUND SOFTWARE	
Drivers	TELEMED Drivers Package for Windows OS
SDK	USGFW2 SDK 4.3.1b68 or later
ULTRASOUND SOFTWARE	
Dimensions W x D x H, mm	111x111x30
Weight, g	TBD
POWER CONSUMPTION	
5 VDC, 2.5 A Max	External AC medical grade power supply (100-240 VAC, 50-60 Hz), Class II
	USB C from the PC